

QUANTITATIVE CHARACTERIZATION OF FORMING PROPERTIES IN PEEK/CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

One of the first indications of unacceptable processing conditions in forming continuous fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites is the onset of surface ply buckling. A surface ply buckling model is presented which depends on the composite's interply shear behavior, interfacial surface tension, and ply bending modulus at the forming temperature and processing rate. A shear fixture was constructed to measure interply shear flow. A power law model represents the shear stress-strain behavior of PEEK/carbon fiber (ICI's APC-2) unidirectional laminates between 366°C and 396°C. Cross-ply laminates split parallel to the 90° fibers during shear testing. The surface ply buckling model provided a conservative estimate of the critical strain rate, and hence forming rate, in comparison to experimental observations of buckling in unidirectional APC-2 laminates at 381°C.

KEYWORDS: Composites, Polymer; Thermoplastic, PEEK; Forming; Shearing; Buckling.

INTRODUCTION

Converting a thermoplastic continuous fiber-reinforced laminate into a complex shape entails a variety of deformation mechanisms. In order to develop a basic forming model for thermoplastic composites, it is desirable to characterize individually these deformation mechanisms. Permeability, interply shear flow, transverse flow, and elastic bending in PEEK/carbon fiber laminates (ICI's APC-2) have been studied independently at processing temperatures for this purpose.

This paper focuses on interply shear flow. Permeability is not a primary concern in forming. Characterization of permeability in APC-2 has been reported (1,2,3). The characterization of elastic bending and transverse flow in APC-2 at processing temperatures has been described (4,5). Wu (5) has developed a surface ply buckling model for forming which is linked directly to elastic bending and interply shear flow. This

model will be reviewed and then the interply shear flow results for APC-2 will be presented. Using these results, an evaluation of the surface ply buckling model will be presented.

BACKGROUND

One of the first signs of failure in matched die forming is surface ply buckling in the composite. Small diameter fibers are prone to buckling under compressive loading. Since the matrix is molten during forming, it is difficult to restrain the fibers from buckling. Thus, one critical element in analyzing forming is to predict the onset of buckling.

Wu (5) has developed a surface ply buckling model which depends on material properties, part shape, and forming conditions. The basis for this model is shown in Figure 1. During forming, the laminate is subjected to compressive stresses at the inside radius of the bend. The compressive stress can be relieved by interply slip. However, the resistance to interply slip leads to a shear stress which impedes the relief of the compressive stresses developed during bending. Consequently, the compressive stress in the surface ply can exceed the buckling stress.

For this buckling to occur, the surface ply must delaminate. The energy required for delamination and buckling of the surface ply is

$$W_t = 2 lb \gamma_s + \pi^4 E h^5 b / (18l^3) \quad (1)$$

where l is the buckling length, b is the width of the ply, h is the thickness of the ply, γ_s is the surface tension of the interply layers, and E is the ply modulus. The most probable buckling length, l_{cr} , is obtained by minimizing W_t with respect to l :

$$l_{cr} = \left\{ \pi^4 E h^5 / (12 \gamma_s) \right\}^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (2)$$

A critical buckling stress, σ_{cr} , is defined as the apparent stress causing delamination and buckling at the critical buckling length:

$$W_{t,min} = \sigma_{cr}^2 h b l_{cr} / 2E \quad (3)$$

Substituting equations 1 and 2 into 3 gives

$$\sigma_{cr} = \left\{ 16 E \gamma_s / (3h) \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (4)$$

Figure 1 illustrates how this critical buckling stress is balanced by an interply shear stress:

$$\sigma_c bh = \tau bL \quad (5)$$

where L is the undelaminated free span. Substituting equation 4 into 5 gives

$$\tau = \left\{ 16E\gamma_s h / (3L^2) \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (6)$$

It will be shown that τ has a power law dependence on the interply shear strain rate:

$$\tau = m\dot{\gamma}^n \quad (7)$$

The interply shear strain rate is proportional to the forming rate (5). Therefore, it is particularly important to determine the quantitative relationship between shear stress and strain rate in the interply region in order to determine what forming conditions result in low shear stresses and hence buckle-free parts. The ply modulus, E , and interply surface tension, γ_s , should be determined at processing conditions in order to estimate the critical buckling stress; and hence, the maximum value of τ based on equation 6. Wu has determined values of E and γ_s for APC-2 (5). The following section describes the measurement of interply shear stress-strain rate properties for APC-2 laminates.

EXPERIMENTAL

A three-plated, uniaxial shear fixture was constructed to characterize interply shear flow. This fixture is illustrated in Figure 2. The fixture is designed to hold two specimens at one time to eliminate any moment caused by an unbalanced fixture structure. The specimens are sandwiched by three hot plates. The two outer plates are attached to a base and remain stationary. The center plate is free to move between the outer plates and thereby impart a shear stress to the specimens. The plates are heated with cartridge heaters and controlled separately by three controllers.

The shear fixture was connected to an Instron Model 1125. The center plate was pulled up at a set speed. Its movement was monitored as the total shear displacement. The pulling force was measured by the load cell and plotted against the shear displacement. The relative movement between specimens and the fixture plates must be eliminated to assure that the measured displacement is solely from the shear deformation of the specimens. Practically, there are two ways to hold specimens on the plates to achieve the non-slip boundary conditions. The first method is to apply forces normal to the surface of the outer plates to hold the entire fixture together. These normal forces will induce transverse flow in the specimens to some extent and destroy the simple shear flow situation planned for the tests. The second way is to prepare the specimens with end tabs on the exterior plies as shown in Figure 3. One of the tabs will be clamped on the center plate and the other will be clamped on the outer plate. When carefully adjusted,

this method will prevent transverse flow and can assure accurate measurement of the shear deformation. This second method was adapted in this research.

Shear tests were conducted at the desired temperatures at various pulling rates. The pulling of the center plate sometimes was purposely stopped during the test to detect the effect of fiber entanglement and to ensure that the force measured was mainly from the shear flow. The measured force usually dropped to within 5% of the original pulling force in less than twenty seconds after stopping. If large residual forces were present, the data were discarded as there might be complicated situations, such as severe fiber entanglement, involved in the test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Shear tests gave consistent results for unidirectional ,16 ply, APC-2 laminates. Normal force was negligible, as the width of the specimens changed little during the tests. Shear flow occurred mainly in interply layers and was not observed through the thickness of individual plies in optical microscopy. Because slippage did not occur in every interply layer, the shear strain rate in interply layers $\dot{\gamma}_i$, was calculated as:

$$\dot{\gamma}_i = V / n_i h_i \quad (8)$$

where V is the pulling-out speed, n_i is the number of slipped interply layers, which was obtained by visually examining tested specimens, and h_i is taken as 5 μm based on the micrographs.

Shear stress versus shear strain rate is plotted logarithmically in Figure 4 for interply shear flow of APC-2 at 381°C. The data could be fitted with a straight line. This fit indicates that a power law model can be used to describe the flow in interply layers. Shear tests at 366°C and 396°C show similar results (Figure 5). This power law behavior has been confirmed by other investigators (6,7). These results imply that the Newtonian fluid assumption used in some process modeling may introduce significant errors in describing thermoplastic composite materials.

Cogswell et al. observed a yield stress of about 300 Pa in their shear tests (8). This yield stress is equivalent to 0.028 kg force for the specimens used, and thus it is too small to be detected in this research.

Groves (7) measured steady shear flow viscosity of APC-2 laminates at 380°C using a Rheometrics Dynamic Spectrometer. As Groves used bulk shear strain rates instead of

interply shear strain rates, his data are converted here into interply shear strain rates based on the following equation:

$$\dot{\gamma} = \dot{\gamma}_i h_i / (h_p + h_i) \quad (9)$$

where $\dot{\gamma}$ and $\dot{\gamma}_i$ are bulk shear strain rate and interply shear strain rate respectively, and h_p and h_i are the thicknesses of a ply and an interply layer respectively. In Groves' study, h_p was 0.125 mm and h_i was 5 μm . Hence one obtains:

$$26 \dot{\gamma} = \dot{\gamma}_i \quad (10)$$

The converted data are compared to the data in this research in Figure 6. Groves' data agree qualitatively with the data of this research, although his data are slightly higher.

The apparent viscosities based on:

$$\eta = \tau / \dot{\gamma}_i \quad (11)$$

in Figures 4-6 are much higher than the neat resin viscosities for PEEK 150 at the corresponding temperatures. Furthermore, the neat PEEK is Newtonian at the corresponding shear rates. The interpretation of such high apparent viscosities in the interply layers is an open issue. Fibers touching in the interply layers could play an important role here. First, these fibers may become entangled, resulting in higher resistance to flow during shear tests. Second, these touching fibers may drag other fibers out from adjacent plies along the direction of motion and, consequently, cause in-plane *intraply* shear in the individual plies. Cogswell observed a greater resistance to flow when using unidirectional APC-2 laminates in similar tests, and saw "beach marks" where there has been shear through the thickness of the individual plies as shown in Figure 7. These "beach marks" were also seen in this research on some of the tested specimens and could be the result of the in-plane, *intraply* shear mentioned above.

In an attempt to eliminate the effect of fiber entanglement, cross-ply specimens (0/90° lay-up with the fiber direction of the 90° plies perpendicular to the shear direction) were subjected to shear testing. The data generated were very erratic and not repeatable. Visual examination of tested cross-ply specimens revealed many splits along the fiber direction in the 90° plies as shown in Figure 8. These splits occurred even before the shear tests reached steady state.

This splitting phenomenon may be explained in different ways. First, from the point of view of the surface tension, one can consider the energy required to tear apart the parallel fibers in a 90° ply. The energy to create one split in a ply, W_{split} , can be estimated as:

$$W_{\text{split}} = 2\gamma_s h_p b \quad (12)$$

where γ_s is the surface tension of PEEK, h_p is the ply thickness, and b is the ply width. Taking γ_s as 30.5 dynes/cm for PEEK (5), h_p as 0.0125 cm, and b as 1 cm yields:

$$W_{\text{split}} = 0.76 \times 10^{-5} \text{ N-cm} \quad (13)$$

The external work to create ply slipping can be written approximately as:

$$W_e = 1/2 P v_s \quad (14)$$

where P is the pulling force and v_s is the distance a ply slips along the pulling direction. In the cross-ply shear tests the lowest pulling load was about 1 N per cm ply width. Therefore, for a ply slippage of about 10% of a ply thickness:

$$W_e = 0.675 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N-cm} \quad (15)$$

The external shear work involved in the interply slipping is about two orders of magnitude higher than the energy to create a split in a 90° ply. This calculation shows that the split along fibers in 90° plies can be easily generated. The above calculation is only a rough comparison in which the energy loss in overcoming the viscous resistance is not considered.

The shear tests used in this research are not successful in measuring the interply shear flow for cross-ply laminates. A fixture modification from pulling shear mode to pushing shear mode and a slight normal force might provide a solution to this problem.

SURFACE PLY BUCKLING EVALUATION

Since it is clear that interply shear flow can be characterized by a power law relationship, equations 6 and 7 can be combined to solve for the shear strain rate:

$$\dot{\gamma}_i = \left\{ 16E\gamma_s h / (3m^2 L^2) \right\}^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (16)$$

This strain rate corresponds to the onset of surface ply buckling. At lower strain rates buckling is not expected.

For a unidirectional laminate subjected to three point bending the shear strain rate is directly proportional to forming speed (3,5). Wu (5) conducted three point bending tests on unidirectional, 16 ply, APC-2 laminates at 381°C at various rates, corresponding to changes in $\dot{\gamma}_i$, and for different spans, corresponding to changes in L . In a three point

bending test, the undelaminated free span is not expected to exceed the distance between the central loading nose and one of the end supports. Estimates of the elastic modulus, E , and surface tension, γ_s , for APC-2 at 381°C are developed elsewhere (3,5). The values for m and n for APC-2 at 381°C are shown in Figure 4. Thus, all the material parameters in equation 16 can be determined.

Figure 9 compares the prediction of the critical shear strain rate for these APC-2 laminates at 381°C with Wu's observations of buckling (3,5). The curve for $E = 583$ MPa is based on independent measurement of E (5). This prediction of the critical shear strain rate is clearly conservative in comparison with the experimental observations. Increasing E by a factor of five to 2915 MPa appears to provide a better separation between no buckling and buckled samples. The dashed curve is an experimentally-based representation of this boundary.

It is encouraging that the surface ply buckling model shows the same trends as the experimental data. However, increasing the elastic modulus by a factor of five to improve the relationship between the model and experimental observations is arbitrary. Further study of the onset of buckling in forming is needed.

CONCLUSIONS

The shear fixture constructed is successful in measuring interply shear flow for unidirectional laminates. The stress-strain rate relationship is fitted by a power law model for the interply shear flow of unidirectional APC-2 laminates. The interfacial viscosity calculated is rate-dependent and is much greater than that of PEEK resin. The shear tests for cross-ply specimens led to splits along fibers in the 90° plies. An estimate of the force required to split 90° plies is much lower than the force measured in shearing 0/90° laminates.

The surface ply buckling model can be modified to incorporate the power law behavior determined for interply shearing. The model provides a conservative estimate of the critical shear strain rate, and hence forming rate, that causes surface ply buckling as compared to experimental observations of buckling in unidirectional APC-2 laminates formed at 381°C.

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Figure 1. The force balance between the interply shear stress and critical buckling stress.

Figure 2. Shear test fixture.

16 ply unidirectional laminate

Figure 3. A schematic of a shear test sample.

Figure 4. Shear stress versus interply shear strain rate for 16 ply, unidirectional, APC-2 laminates at 381°C.

Figure 5. Shear stress versus interply shear strain rate for 16 ply, unidirectional, APC-2 laminates at 366°C and 396°C.

Figure 6. Comparison of interply shear apparent viscosities for APC-2 laminates. Groves' data are reproduced from Figure 5 of (7).

Figure 7. "Beach marks" observed on some unidirectional shear specimens, reproduced from (9).

Figure 8. The splits in 90° plies observed in cross-ply specimens after shear testing.

Figure 9. A comparison of experimental observations of buckling in forming with the predicted shear strain rate for the onset of surface ply buckling versus the free span length for 16 ply, unidirectional, APC-2 laminates at 381°C.